

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Chemical Investigation of *Mollugo hirta*

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Previously the bitter constituents of the plant *Mollugo spergula* were characterized as saponins. Two new triterpenoid saponogens, spergulagenin A' and spergulagenic acid¹ were isolated by acid hydrolysis of the above saponins. The structure² and stereochemistry⁴ of spergulagenic acid has been established as 3 β -hydroxy- Δ^{12} -olean-28, 30-dioic acid. Spergulagenin A has been found to be a pentacyclic triterpene with a novel skeleton³.

Chemical examination of another species, *Mollugo hirta* (Syn. *M. lotoides*), is reported here. It is an annual shrub and is used in diarrhoea, as a purgative and as a cure for boils and pains in the limbs⁵.

The alcoholic extract of the defatted plant material (whole plant) was found to be rich in saponin. From the alcoholic extract a saponin was obtained which showed a single spot in TLC. Acid-hydrolysis of the above saponin, however, furnished a neutral aglycone which showed two spots in TLC. Repeated crystallisation of the above aglycone mixture from ethanol furnished a homogeneous colourless crystalline product, C₃₀H₅₂O₄, m.p. 250-52°, [α]_D²⁵ +58.5° (Pyridine). It gave pink $\rightarrow$ brown colour in the Liebermann-Burchard test. It appears to be a new triterpenoid saponogenin and has been named as 'mollugogenol A'. Its UV-spectrum did not show any absorption in the region 200-360 m μ . The IR-spectrum (Nujol mull) of mollugogenol-A showed a broad band in the region 3295-3400 cm⁻¹ for hydroxyl groups.

Mollugogenol A on heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride furnished a tetra-acetate, C₃₆H₆₀O₈, m.p. 230-32°. Due to insolubility of mollugogenol-A in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride its colour reaction with tetranitromethane for unsaturation could not be performed. Its tetra-acetate, however, did not respond to the above test. Moreover, the tetra-acetate did not decolorize a solution of bromine in carbon tetrachloride, nor did it consume any perbenzoic acid. All the above experiments together with the absence of any terminal absorption in the UV-spectrum showed mollugogenol A to be a completely saturated compound.

1. Chakrabarti and Barua, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 42, 197.
2. Chakrabarti *et al.*, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 283.
3. Chakrabarti *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 22, 1431.
4. Unpublished data.
5. Chakrabarti, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
6. Chopra *et al.*, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 168.

Mollugogenol A did not react with periodic acid thus showing the absence of any α -glycol system in it. Oxidation of mollugogenol A with CrO_3 -acetic acid furnished a neutral colourless product, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$, m.p. $252\text{--}53^\circ$ (decomp.) which did not respond to alcoholic ferric chloride test thereby eliminating the possibility of it being an enolizable α or β -diketone. It responded to Zimmermann test for 3-keto group⁷ thus showing the presence of a secondary hydroxyl group at C-3 position in mollugogenol A.

Mollugogenol A, a completely saturated triterpene having a molecular formula, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$, with four hydroxyl groups, must be pentacyclic in nature. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that only a few completely saturated pentacyclic triterpenes have so far been reported in literature.

Further work on the constitution of mollugogenol A is in progress.

Procedure. Air dried powdered plant material (whole plant, 600 g.) was defatted with pet. ether (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$). The defatted plant material was Soxhleted with rectified spirit when a saponin precipitated out. It was filtered and the residue (3 g.) was found to be homogeneous in TLC over silica gel G (solvent system—butanol: ethanol: water—5:1:4 v/v). The residue was hydrolysed with 5% aq. alcoholic (EtOH: water—1:1) hydrochloric acid. The aglycone part, thus obtained showed two spots in TLC over silica gel G (solvent system—benzene: ethylacetate: methanol—7:2:1 v/v). From the aglycone part only neutral saponin was obtained. It was repeatedly crystallized from ethanol (charcoal) to give mollugogenol A as a colourless, homogeneous product, m.p. $250\text{--}52^\circ$. (Found: C, 75.55; H, 11.12%, mol. wt. 478 (Rast). $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 75.63; H, 10.92%; mol. wt. 476).

Mollugogenol A (200 mg) on heating with pyridine (2 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) gave a crystalline tetra-acetate, m.p. $230\text{--}32^\circ$. (Found: C, 70.77; H, 9.56. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 70.81; H, 9.32%).

A methanolic solution (20 ml) of mollugogenol A (50 mg.) was treated with an aqueous solution of periodic acid (50 mg. in 0.1 ml water) at room temp. On working up unchanged material, m.p. $248\text{--}50^\circ$, was obtained. To a solution of mollugogenol A (300 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was added slowly a solution of CrO_3 (300 mg, 1 ml of water and 7 ml of glacial acetic acid) at room temperature with constant stirring for 5 hr. Chromic acid solution (3 ml) was added till brown colour persisted. Excess chromic acid was destroyed by addition of methanol and then worked up in the usual way when a neutral, colourless compound, m.p. $252\text{--}53^\circ$ (dec.) was obtained. It depressed the m.p. of mollugogenol A. (Found: 76.78; H, 9.0. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 76.91; H, 9.40%).

All m.p.s are uncorrected. Spraying reagent used for TLC is a mixture (1:1) of 10% ethanolic sulphuric acid and 10% ethanolic acetic anhydride solution.

The author wishes to express her thanks to Dr. D. M. Bose, Director and Dr. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, for their interest in the work. The author is indebted to Dr. A. K. Barua, Reader in Chemistry, Bose Institute, for stimulating discussions and constructive criticism. Thanks are due to Dr. S. C. Pakraishi, Scientist, Indian Institute for Experimental Medicine, Calcutta, for kindly recording the IR spectra and the National Institute of Sciences of India for financial assistance.

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Received December 30, 1966,

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